
Economics of Information

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Abstract:

This paper deals with the concept of economies of Information. It highlights the comparative phenomena of information of economics and economics of information. Information economics perceives information as a resource of importance, and its role in all economic activities, as a resource for production, growth and development. Economics of information, however, deals with the management aspect of information systems and services with reference to prudent planning in the deposition of resources so as to avoid unnecessary waste or expense.

Introduction:

The information handling activities are central to the operation of any organization. Information service comprises generation and collection of information, processing of information and information retrieval, current awareness services, selective dissemination of information, computerization of database and information transfer etc. In the rapidly changing society, the barriers difficulty in obtaining and exploiting information are increasing. It is true that the information gap between the source of information and the recipient has been widened. At one end is the complex universe of information and at the other end, there is the population of users with their various needs. These two ends are to be bridged and interlinked. Here, information centers come in handy. They act as an agent of information transfer by streamlining the available information to the right users at the right time.

Primary aim of information service is putting the knowledge to work. The primitive civilized men preserved knowledge in clay tablets, stones, inscriptions in caves, etc. but the modern

man preserves knowledge in books, audio and video cassettes and microchips. The real gain of information is to use it for economic benefits. In the words of Eliahu Hoffman " Information is an aggregate (collection or accumulation) of statements or facts or figures which are conceptually, by way of reasoning, logic, idea, or any other mental mode of operation, interrelated."

Economic Characteristics of Information:

The characteristics of information are distinctly different from the characters of other products and services. This distinction was a problem in determining its impact on market activities and decision making. Information economics needs to be discussed at the micro level dealing with problem of information in terms of uncertainty. In nonmarket institutions dealing with public goods and services, information operates as a vital factor. Therefore, information flow in these institutions should be considered as an important to identify gaps and to establish information support facilities. Economic characteristics of information are as under.

- Information is sharable as well as exchangeable.
- Information increases with use.
- Information is compressible, able to be summarized.
- Information is acquired at a definite measurable cost.
- Information possesses a definite value, depending upon its user. It may be quantified and treated as an accountable asset.
- Information may vary in value overtime in an entirely unpredictable way.
- Information is amenable to the use of cost accounting techniques and
- Information is a source of both economical and political power.

Information Economy:

It is another aspect of information economics. The components of an information economy include-

- Information work force.
- Information goods and services.
- Information machinery.
- Information industry and markets and the information infrastructure. The Pricing of information has also to be determined on the basis of cost as well as the market conditions. The quality of information products and services alone would determine a sure and steady market.

Information economics is important for library and information professionals due to following two reasons.

1. The recognition of information as a vital factor for growth and prosperity of country.
2. To expand the job opportunities.

Therefore, "Due to the rapid change in the scenario of constraints of resources, cost inflation and competition, market has become necessary for libraries too. Increasing competition from commercial

information has compelled librarians to consider implementing marketing techniques in their services."

Scope of Information Economics:

Considering information as human capital, the significance and effect of this capital are analyzed as a factor of economic growth and development. Information problems relate to market, trading in commodities, insurance, labour finance etc. are examined in relation to buyers and sellers. The information is examined with reference to public decisions and public goods, production and distribution of new knowledge, central planning etc. Empirical research, theoretical analysis and applied enquiry get special consideration as methodological aspects of the economics of information. "At the macro economic level, the absorption, or assimilation, of increasingly modern technologies, and adoption to a change of industrial structure, are increasingly becoming the critical components of transformation to a competitive society. The transition from our present stage of knowledge levels to that of innovation capability and management of newly created knowledge as a strategic asset is very crucial in India is to maintain and improve its growing competitive position. This transition process has to be accelerated."

Information Measurement:

Costing determines the price at which an information product or service can be offered, but price cannot be determined on the basis of cost as the quality of the product or services is very crucial factor in fixing the price. Apart from the difficulties of determining the cost of a product or service in which a number of inputs are involved, other costs such as opportunity cost are to be taken into account. Opportunity cost represent the cost of

foregone alternatives, the need to satisfy ones want at sacrifice of another.

Determining the value of information is a complex matter which lies at the heart of information economy. Value of information is highly subjective as it is to be judged and measured by the person who is seeking the information, but the problem of measurement of information is elusive and evasive as it is difficult to determine a unit of information. Again attempts at measuring value by means of cost benefit analysis may also present the problem of assigning a monetary value for the benefit.

Information Industry and Emergence of New markets:

Expanding new dimensions of information and services have given rise to a new information industry and a new market. Naturally these type of industries and markets have emerged in countries with a highly developed services sector and sufficient local demand to support them. However for reasons of scale and profit they have outgrown national boundaries and the information industry is now a truly international affair. There are fierce competitions and new sets of trans-border flow, intellectual property rights, tariff wars and various kinds of trade barriers have emerged.

Information Infrastructure:

The information infrastructure of an information economy comprises –

- Education and training
- Research and Development
- Mass media
- Telecommunications

The computer and telecommunication technologies which would make it possible to assess these from any part of the globe, would greatly improve information accessibility and availability.

Advantages of Economics of Information:

1. The value and importance of information have been highlighted so well in information economy that they are likely to strengthen our professional commitments.
2. The scope and dimensions of information economics open up new area of study and research for us to pursue.
3. A new type of job market is emerging which expands the scope for professional opportunities for employment.

Conclusion:

Information economics perceives information as a resource of importance and examine its role in all economic activities as a factor of production, growth and development. All economic issues are discussed with reference to the role of information in markets, decision making, cost, price and value, monopoly, competition etc. At the macro level, the national economy is viewed as an information economy with particular reference to the contribution of information to the national gross product, with information products and services and Information Technology as the main instrument of change. Economics of information is the prudent planning of households, institutions and Governments in the disposition of resource, so as to avoid unnecessary waste or expenses.

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